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An Inductive Evaluation of the Power of Radio Information: A Retrospective Study of the 1967-1970 Nigerian Civil War

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*Civil War,
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This study evaluated the efficacy of the messages that were aired over the radio during the 1967-1970 Nigerian civil war. It further aimed to investigate whether modern radio broadcasts have the potential to be used in the same manner and to the same degree of success as their historical analogues in the service of the cause of sustainable development. Hence, the study employed the inoculation theory and Hugh Rank's model of persuasion in its theoretical framework. The research was conducted using an inductive methodology, and the interview inventory served as the primary research instrument. The sampling method used is convenient sampling, and the collated information was examined based on central themes and then discussed. The results of the research provide novel information on the function of radio in the broadcast of safety information during the civil war, as well as its use for the mobilisation of military forces at that time. The fact that there is so little academic material about media communication and radio engagement during the civil war in Nigeria presented the current research with a challenge that was empirical in nature. This shortage also played a key part in amplifying the essence of the study, which is aimed at bridging the existing vacuum within the academic discourse. According to the study, listening to radio broadcasts during the Civil War saved the lives of most people. It became clear from the study that radio broadcasts throughout the Civil War provided a deliberate, well-thought-out, and very compelling framework for the distressed population that was designed to defuse rather than escalate tensions. The study further found that the radio is a helpful companion because it can reach many people regardless of where they live; this suggests that the radio could be used to disseminate strategic information that would inspire people to comply with sustainable development goals.

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INTRODUCTION

The acquisition and dissemination of information play a pivotal role in all facets of human endeavours and interactions (Dominick, 2009). Effective completion of all tasks, assignments, and workouts necessitates the establishment of robust intercommunication channels among the individuals involved. In instances where the transmission of information occurs at a reduced rate or experiences a disruption, the resultant consequences will manifest as inefficacious. The recognition of information as a crucial resource that necessitates sufficient development is primarily attributed to its feedback effect on society. Consequently, a society devoid of adequate communication infrastructure and mechanisms for information dissemination will invariably find itself trailing behind its technologically superior counterparts in terms of societal progress.

The undeniable progression of radio technology as a medium for the dissemination of news, education, and entertainment has been evident since its initial introduction (Owumalam, 2006). Despite the advancements in television and the internet, radio continues to maintain its significance as a crucial medium of Communication, particularly in regions that are characterised by underdevelopment. While radio continues to maintain a significant presence in

contemporary society, its position and prospects within the fiercely competitive media landscape remain uncertain. Indeed, there have been prognostications positing that the radio industry will experience a decline in market penetration due to the burgeoning popularity of digital media. Despite the discontinuation of certain stations, the radio medium experienced a notable resurgence due to the widespread adoption of inventive programming formats and the introduction of stereo signals. Despite a perceived decline in the popularity of radio, the technology has managed to endure due to its innovative utilisation in various domains, such as transportation, wherein it is integrated with automobiles (Apochi, 2007).

Despite the prevalence of smartphones and the availability of streaming content, radio remains a significant medium that fulfils both personal and commercial functions (May, 2013). Radio broadcasts serve as a medium through which listeners are both informed and enlightened regarding pertinent societal issues. Subjects such as politics, business, contemporary occurrences, social inequity, labour, and other related areas are extensively propagated with the intention of enhancing individuals' awareness. Through the elevation of listeners' awareness regarding their civic obligations and privileges, radio possesses the potential to function as a catalyst for transformative societal shifts (Akingbulu & Hendrik, 2010). Individuals engage with radio

broadcasting for a multitude of purposes and during diverse temporal intervals, including the early hours of the day when preparing for professional or educational commitments, the twilight hours when seeking solace in the company of loved ones, or while traversing distances in a vehicular manner. The act of engaging in radio consumption, whether in solitude or in a collective setting, primarily serves the purpose of acquiring information.

In contrast to the conclusion of the initial republic, wherein the Nigerian civil war endured for a span of thirty months, contemporary society benefits from an expanded spectrum of information dissemination facilitated by technological progress. Notwithstanding this, radio continues to hold immense significance in contemporary society. The medium of radio transcends its conventional role as a platform for Disc Jockeys, news dissemination, and musical entertainment. The essence of radio lies in the fundamental aspects of companionship and establishing a personal connection, as elucidated by Akingbulu (2010). In a retrospective analysis of the civil war, it is evident that all factions involved in the conflict, including the governing bodies and the non-combatant population, were equipped with real-time information through the utilisation of radio broadcasts (Opejobi, 2015). The continuous transmission facilitated unrestricted access to real-time information at the convenience of individuals.

Given the defunct state of the Biafran border, radio transmissions emerged as a highly prized means of gathering intelligence for all parties involved in the conflict. In the midst of these pivotal circumstances, characterised by significant disruptions in the accessibility of postal offices and centres, the significance of radio technology has been demonstrated (Kristilolu, 2007). The majority of radios in use during that period were powered by batteries and featured a hand-crank mechanism, enabling their operation in the absence of electrical power. In contemporary times, the utility of radio extends beyond its conventional role as a medium for receiving crucial alerts and messages amidst

natural calamities. The platform serves as a conduit for the perpetual dissemination of information pertaining to various subjects such as regional athletics, communal gatherings, and extraordinary occasions, as well as promotional content from nearby enterprises, among others. The primary objective of this study will entail an in-depth analysis of the dissemination of radio messages and information within the now-defunct Biafran and Nigerian territories, with a particular emphasis on examining the extent to which this phenomenon enhanced Communication. Furthermore, this research aims to explore the potential applicability of these communication advancements in contemporary times, specifically in the realm of facilitating efficient information management, thereby fostering sustainable development.

Research Problem

Concerns have been articulated regarding the expeditious proliferation of radio stations and the extent to which they are operating in the public interest vis-à-vis the interests of advertisers and profit-oriented proprietors. There exists a dichotomous perspective regarding the impact of radio on global cultures. Critics contend that radio serves as a vehicle for the dissemination of Western values, thereby exerting a profound influence on diverse societies. Conversely, proponents assert that radio assumes a crucial role in facilitating the transmission of indigenous customs and traditions, thereby preserving local cultural heritage (Ngoa, 2011). Conversely, there exists a school of thought positing that radio, through its facilitation of enhanced proximity between the government and its policies with the populace, has engendered a heightened level of awareness among rural residents pertaining to matters encompassing governmental policy, national occurrences and global events, among others. The utilisation of radio as a medium holds significant potential in facilitating the advancement and development of a nation.

While certain philosophical perspectives posit that the media possesses a negligible influence on society, alternative viewpoints contend that the

dissemination of information pertaining to specific subjects, when brought to the attention of individuals within specific circumstances, does indeed exert an impact. The objective of this research endeavour is to scrutinise the influence of radio during the nascent stage of the Nigerian civil war and to ascertain the rationale behind its potential to exert a more substantial influence on the nation's pursuit of sustainable development, considering the extensive endorsement it has already garnered within Nigeria.

Research Objectives

- To assess individuals' experiences with radio broadcasts during the 1967-1970 Nigerian Civil War
- To ascertain if information was effectively managed through radio broadcasts even in the face of the crisis.
- To find out if the radio can be as effective today as it was during the civil war in fostering the attainment of the Sustainable Development Goals

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Development of Radio Broadcast in Nigeria

Tracing its origins to the year 1932, when the inaugural British Empire service emanated from Daventry, England, the urban centre of Lagos emerged as the focal point of Nigeria's radio broadcasting sector. Upon the strategic determination of the British administration in London to establish a connection between its West African colonies and the metropole, namely Britain, the subsequent course of action entailed the establishment of radio transmission infrastructure in Nigeria (Okorie, 2006). The anticipated outcome of this connection was twofold: firstly, it was expected to serve as a potent tool for disseminating propaganda on behalf of the colonial power, namely Britain, and secondly, it was seen to acquire knowledge about the British populace and the wider world (Ikime, 2002).

During the epoch of British colonial governance, the British Broadcasting Corporation disseminated broadcasts to territories formerly under their dominion with the intention of attaining the said objective. During that period, Nigeria exhibited a pronounced inclination towards the establishment of a radio station, prompting the colonial office in London to undertake measures aimed at materialising this aspiration. To expedite the delivery of broadcasting service within the colonial empire, synchronise said services with the operations of the esteemed British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC), and harness their potential as effective tools for advancing both local and imperial objectives, the colonial secretary in London, during that period, resolved to convene a committee tasked with deliberating upon and proposing viable measures to attain these objectives (Ikime, 2002). The committee has granted approval for the implementation of radio transmission within the Nigerian context. The statement also predicted that through the utilisation of wired fidelity, a fusion of BBC content and locally produced programming by the colonial government would be transmitted to the colonies.

The committee recognised the evident necessity of overseeing these televised programmes to safeguard the public from potential exposure to offensive or subversive material. In accordance with the broadcasting modality, individuals who subscribed to the service were required to remit a recurring monthly payment. In return, they were furnished with a rudimentary and improvised apparatus comprising of wiring infrastructure that facilitated the connection of loudspeaker devices within their respective domiciles (Akingula, 2006). The service of the British Broadcasting Corporation, which had its inception in Daventry, England, was disseminated from the Lagos facility of the BBC (Moemeka, 1985). The proliferation of radio services in Nigeria witnessed a surge in response to the escalating demand, prompting the establishment of new broadcasting stations in regions extending beyond the nation's economic hub, Lagos. In

contradistinction to the modality of “wireless broadcasting,” which encompasses the transmission of programmes through the medium of radio waves, the present mode of broadcasting is commonly denoted as “wired broadcasting” (Electromagnetic waves). The advent of broadcasting in Nigeria can be attributed to a convergence of fortuitous circumstances. In its nascent stage, the broadcasting service primarily entailed the retransmission of BBC programmes through a relay system that bore a striking resemblance to the mechanical infrastructure of Britain’s radio relay exchange system, which had been operational since the 1920s. The designation “Radio Distribution Service” was deliberately selected to accurately convey the inherent characteristics and scope of the services rendered, commonly abbreviated as RDS (Elaigwu, 2005).

According to Ojebode’s (2005) assertion, the introduction of the Radio Distribution System (RDS) in Nigeria was instigated by the colonial office in London. This initiative was spearheaded by the engineers of the Posts and Telegraphs (P&T) Department, who had already established a network of 13 stations across various Nigerian locations, namely Katsina, Lagos, Zaria, Jos, Ilorin, Sokoto, Maiduguri, Port Harcourt, Onitsha, Calabar, Warri, Abeokuta, and Ijebu-Ode. During the period in which the British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) was engaged in the experimental phase of transmitting signals via short wave, the responsibility of monitoring these transmissions was entrusted to the esteemed personnel of the Post and Telegraph (P&T) engineering department. As per the scholarly work of Oyero (2003), the advent of wired broadcasting in Nigeria in the year 1932 entailed the transmission of programmes originating from England, facilitated by the utilisation of local presenters during that era. Every participant was obligated to submit an initial payment equivalent to three months’ worth of rent in advance, succeeded by a recurring monthly subscription fee of fifty pence.

By the year 1939, the Registered Distribution System (RDS) had amassed a total of over two thousand officially authorised receivers, yet its

subscriber base remained below the one-thousand mark. By the year 1944, distribution centres had been established in the ports of Lagos, Ibadan, Kaduna, Enugu, Calabar, and Port Harcourt, along with their respective inland counterparts. By the year 1949, a span of five years after the initial implementation, the aggregate number of subscribers had reached a count of 9,000, all of whom were connected via wired connections to a network of 10 stations dispersed throughout the nation. In that year, the total number of registered radios in Nigeria amounted to 4,562 units. Although the RDS did provide a limited range of distinct programming, most of its transmissions remained within the purview of the BBC’s external service. The production of programmes by the information department of the colonial government and their subsequent broadcast by the service was limited in scope, with only a modest number of such initiatives being undertaken. The commencement of the broadcast services occurred promptly at 5:00 a.m. and concluded at 12:00 am daily, interspersed with a brief interval during the midday period. In 1936, the colonial administration assigned the Plymouth Committee the responsibility of formulating a comprehensive strategy for the implementation of wireless broadcasting in Nigeria. The resultant recommendations put forth by the committee were subsequently embraced and implemented by the esteemed British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC).

In the year 1948, the colonial office issued a directive to the British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) to undertake an assessment of the broadcasting landscape in Nigeria, Ghana, Sierra Leone, and Gambia. The objective was to obtain necessary approvals for the expeditious establishment of effective broadcasting services in these respective territories (Moemeka, 1985). The assignment was bestowed upon a pair of British engineers, namely L. W. Turners from the British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) and F.A.W Bryon from the Telecommunications Department. During this temporal juncture, a succinct electromagnetic wave transmission facility, colloquially referred to as “Radio

Nigeria,” was duly established in the city of Lagos with the primary objective of retransmitting the Lagos Radio Distribution System (RDS) programme. As has been previously elucidated, the primary purpose of the RDS, or Radio Distribution System, was to disseminate BBC programming to a wider audience. However, during the evening hours, a designated time slot was allocated for the transmission of localised content, encompassing news, entertainment, and governmental affairs (Ojebode, 2005).

The commencement of direct radio transmission in Nigeria was inaugurated in Lagos in April 1951 with the establishment of the Nigerian Broadcasting Service (NBC). To achieve comprehensive nationwide coverage, the network underwent expansion to incorporate the urban areas of Enugu (in September 1952), Kaduna (in May 1952), and Ibadan (in April 1955), whereby the previously utilised re-diffusion relay stations were upgraded and converted into fully operational NBS stations. In 1957, the Nigerian Broadcasting Service underwent a transformation into a statutory corporation known as the Nigerian Broadcasting Corporation, as per the provisions outlined in an Act of Parliament that received approval from Queen Elizabeth II of England.

As per Okusan’s (2005) research, a significant development occurred in 1959 when the Nigerian Broadcasting Corporation (NBC) witnessed the dissolution of its monopoly as the exclusive purveyor of broadcasting services in Nigeria. This transformation transpired due to the strategic utilisation of the Nigerian Broadcasting Corporation (NBC) Ordinance or Act by the Action Group (AG) government in the Western region. Consequently, the establishment of the Western Nigerian Broadcasting Corporation (WNBC) materialised, thereby enabling the AG government to realise its aspiration of owning and operating a radio station. Notably, the headquarters of this newly formed entity were situated in Ibadan, the capital of the Western region. On the auspicious date of March 21, 1951, within the geographical confines of Ibadan, Nigeria, the esteemed Chief Obafemi Awolowo, who held the distinguished position of Western

Region Premier at the time, undertook the noble endeavour of establishing the Action Group (AG), a political organisation that espoused the ideals of Nigerian nationalism.

The inception of the Eastern Nigeria Broadcasting Service (ENBS) on October 1, 1960, can be attributed to the visionary leadership of Michael Iheonukara Okpara Ahankara, the esteemed Premier of the Eastern Region. Similarly, the Broadcasting Corporation of Northern Nigeria (BCNN) Radio/Television, which came into existence in 1962, owes its existence to the pioneering efforts of Sir Ahmadu Bello, the distinguished Premier of the Northern Region. Subsequently, additional constituent governments promptly emulated this course of action by instituting their own broadcasting platforms.

The Nigerian Civil War (1967-1970)

Following a prolonged period of political volatility and societal unrest in Nigeria, coupled with the unfortunate loss of lives among the Igbo populace residing in the northern region during the initial and subsequent stages of 1966, the prevailing circumstances rapidly deteriorated. Consequently, these compelled individuals of Igbo descent to undertake a mass exodus from various parts of the federation, seeking refuge in their ancestral homeland (Kristilolu, 2007). Lieutenant-Colonel Odumegwu Ojukwu, the esteemed Military Governor of Eastern Nigeria, acquiesced to the fervent Igbo demands and, in an autonomous fashion, proclaimed the independence of Biafra on the momentous date of May 30, 1967, after the fruitless culmination of negotiations. The individual in question presented the post-coup violence, which resulted in the unfortunate loss of lives among the Easterners (specifically the Igbo people), as the principal catalyst for the disintegration of the nation. The presence of a substantial volume of petroleum reserves within the region played a pivotal role in precipitating the commencement of a civil conflict in Nigeria, owing to the profound importance of this resource in the nation’s economic framework. As per the scholarly work of Minahan (2002), it can be inferred that Enugu, the administrative

centre of the secessionist state of Biafra, experienced a significant decline in its socio-political structure near the commencement of the Nigerian civil war, culminating on July 6, 1967.

One of the contributing factors that precipitated the onset of the Civil War was the apprehension surrounding the potential ascendancy of tribal influence (Ihunna, 2002). Primarily, it was this prevailing apprehension that precipitated the inaugural instance of a military coup d'état in Nigeria on the 15th of January 1966, thereby ushering General Johnson Aguiyi-Ironsi into a position of authority. The cessation of civilian governance under Prime Minister Abubakar Tafawa Balewa was brought about by a violent coup d'état orchestrated by a faction of five majors, with Major C.K. Nzeogwu, an Igbo Nigerian military officer assuming leadership (Mainasara, 1982). Aguiyi-Ironsi assumed leadership of Nigeria amidst a complex socio-political landscape characterised by profound divisions stemming from ethnic and religious tensions. The 1966 coup did not target any high-profile individuals of Igbo descent, and it is worth noting that the primary beneficiaries of this coup were the Igbo population residing in the eastern region of Nigeria. The facts engendered a perception within the northern region of the nation that it had been subject to an Igbo conspiracy. The initiation of the coup d'état was purportedly attributed to the Igbo tribe, as it was observed that no Igbo army officer met their demise during the coup, which subsequently facilitated the ascension of Aguiyi-Ironsi to a position of authority (Abubakar, 2002).

Aguiyi-Ironsi's tenure as the leader of Nigeria spanned from 16 January 1966 to 29 July 1966, abruptly concluding with his assassination at the hands of a faction of mutinous Northern Nigerian military personnel. This group, under the leadership of Major Murtala Mohammed and comprising individuals such as Captain Theophilus Danjuma, Lieutenant Muhammadu Buhari, Lieutenant Sani Abacha, and Lieutenant Ibrahim Babaginda, orchestrated a rebellion

against Aguiyi-Ironsi's administration, commonly referred to as the 1966 Nigerian counter-coup (Kristilolu, 2007). The ascension of General Yakubu Gowon to power was facilitated by the occurrence of this coup, as portrayed by Elaigwu (2005). The failure of General Aguiyi to take punitive action against the perpetrators of the January 1966 coup, which had facilitated his ascent to power, had a discernible impact on the prevailing tribal sentiments. It was widely perceived that General Aguiyi, being a participant in the subsequent July coup, bore the responsibility of holding accountable those individuals responsible for orchestrating and executing the January 1966 coup. Regrettably, General Aguiyi's omission in this regard engendered a sense of dissatisfaction and disillusionment among various tribal factions. The absence of punitive measures on his part is widely regarded as having established a firm foundation for the eruption of the Civil War in 1967 (Okusan, 2005).

One additional factor contributing to the outbreak of the 1967 Civil War can be attributed to the discordant interplay between the personalities of Colonel Yakubu Gowon and Lt. Colonel Ojukwu. According to Ihunna (2002), it is noteworthy to mention that Colonel Yakubu Gowon, while assuming the role of Head of State, did not hold the highest rank among his military peers. During that period, Brigadier Ogundipe held the esteemed position of the highest-ranking military officer. Henceforth, it was the conviction of Lieutenant Colonel Ojukwu that the appointment of Brigadier Ogundipe as the Head of State would have been more appropriate, as opposed to Colonel Gowon. In addition to this, it is noteworthy to mention that Lieutenant Colonel Ojukwu held a superior rank compared to Colonel Gowon, thus leading to his reluctance to adhere to the directives issued by the latter. This assertion is purportedly associated with his proclamation to secede the Eastern region from the nation-state (Ihunna, 2002). The division of the secessionist Biafran State from Nigeria is shown in the image below;

Figure 1: Division of the Biafran Republic

Source: <https://twitter.com/nigeriacivilwar/status/1406971086948950019?s=48&t=G0BVbvb5swczTZTk85jC-w>

Effectiveness of Radio Technology During the Nigerian Civil War

The establishment of Radio Biafra can be attributed to the Government of the Republic of Biafra, with its origins rooted in the historical context of the Nigerian-Biafran conflict during the 1960s and '70s (Ugochukwu, 2010). During the period spanning from May 30th, 1967, to January 15th, 1970, the designated radio station of the Biafran Republic operated under the appellation of Radio Biafra, a nomenclature that drew its inspiration from the geographical region known as the Bight of Biafra. The predominant demographic composition of the region under consideration, namely Southeast Nigeria, was characterised by a significant presence of

individuals belonging to the Igbo ethnic group. It is noteworthy to mention that this particular ethnic group played a pivotal role in initiating the secessionist movement, which can be attributed to a confluence of economic, religious, and cultural factors that engendered tensions within the broader Nigerian context.

In a previous study, Akinyemi (1972) highlighted the dearth of credibility in both radio broadcasts and government announcements, emphasising the inability of the average Biafran citizen to discern between these two sources of information. As a result, a considerable number of adolescent males within the populace commenced engaging with transistor radios, thereby yielding advantageous outcomes for individuals possessing varying

degrees of literacy. This phenomenon can be attributed to the fact that individuals lacking proficiency in the English language were able to comprehend audio transmissions delivered in vernacular languages, such as Igbo or Pidgin English. The denizens of Biafra colloquially designated Radio Biafra as their auditory conduit.

The radio station's dissemination of educational discourse and persuasive messaging exerted a substantial influence in galvanising the Biafran populace to lend their backing to the military campaign. Divergent perspectives were observed among individuals regarding the radio station's broadcasts amidst the conflict. Certain individuals perceived the radio as a tool of conflict, whereas others regarded it as a vital means of connectivity to the external realm, serving as a conduit for news and information that could potentially facilitate their endurance and instil optimism. As posited by Omaka (2017), the radio medium served as a subversive tool within the realm of mass media, effectively employed in the propagation of propaganda during times of conflict. The individual in question astutely observed that radio continues to be employed by governmental entities and revolutionary factions due to its expeditious dissemination capabilities. In the context of the civil war, it is pertinent to acknowledge the enduring significance of Biafra radio despite its devaluation. This medium played a crucial role in providing sustenance and support to the populace while concurrently fostering a sense of communal solidarity that bolstered the motivation of individuals amidst the conflict (Stremlau, 2015).

The propagandists affiliated with the Biafran administration were entrusted with the responsibility of fostering cohesion among a populace that demonstrated a willingness to endure adversity while simultaneously persuading them that any alternative course of action would result in utter devastation. The underlying objective of the propaganda disseminated within the region of Biafra was to instil a sense of resilience and determination among the beleaguered populace, urging them to persist in their struggle until its ultimate culmination. The

primary objective of Biafran propaganda was to enhance global consciousness regarding the conflict and exert diplomatic pressure on the Gowon administration to acknowledge Biafra's inherent entitlement to self-governance (Ugochukwu, 2010). In pursuit of its stated objective, the Biafran government endeavoured to persuade individuals across the globe of the purported genocidal nature of the Nigerian military's operations, which were primarily directed towards the Biafran populace, predominantly comprised of the Igbo ethnic group. The utilisation of the harrowing visual documentation depicting the Igbo atrocities of 1966 proved to be highly efficacious in the dissemination of propaganda beyond national borders. In addition to the circumstances, it is noteworthy to highlight that the inclusion of visual representations depicting emaciated children from the region of Biafra served to enhance the sense of urgency surrounding the issue at hand, rendering it impossible to disregard.

Theoretical Framework

Theories are observations that help explain or clarify a subject. McGuire's inoculation theory, developed in response to a situation in which stopping one person from being convinced by another is the goal, provides the theoretical foundation for this study. The concept is analogous to a paradigm for defending persuasive efforts by presenting opponents with reasons against those efforts and giving supporters of those ideas ammunition to fight those arguments. Therefore, the concept offers ways in which people might use language to protect their own values. An inoculation message, as described by Compton (2013), has two main components, and the word "threat" in this context suggests an imminent attack on the recipient's worldview. That individual is self-aware enough to know how easily swayed he or she may be. When a person feels threatened by his own ideas and emotions, he may take extreme measures to protect his worldview. The inoculation message should both identify persons who are vulnerable to persuasion attempts and hint at possible retaliatory measures (Joshua & Michael, 2005).

Today, information comes at us from every direction and every medium imaginable. Every day, we are subjected to a barrage of efforts that aim to sway us in one way or another. There is a need for knowledge on countering such persuasive strategies. The idea proposes a strategy for overcoming the effects of unfavourable influence.

Hugh Rank also offers a very basic model of persuasion, in which he depicts the two fundamental (and opposing) patterns of intensification and downplay that are common to many persuasive situations.

Figure 2: Hugh Rank's Model of Persuasion

Source: <https://studylib.net/doc/8769747/rank-s-intensify-downplay-schema>

Intensification is a technique used by persuasive communicators to emphasise points that they believe the target audience should give additional weight to while filtering what is not deemed fit for consumption (Rank, 1991), hence setting the agenda for public discourse. The study's use of two theoretical frameworks proves radio's persuasive function in the injection of well-crafted messages into an audience. The radio's usefulness did not end with the end of the thirty-month civil war in Nigeria. People in this ward used the radio, which broadcast messages in a reassuring and incriminating tone, to their advantage to protect themselves. It is important to remember that the radio had a genuine role in political propaganda during the war, as both sides used it to convince citizens and foreigners alike that their side deserved to win.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Observation and experiment, as outlined by Bryman (2014), are at the heart of an inductive research approach. To provide an account of anything happening in the actual world, one must first see and understand it. This research makes findings about its topic using the radio's function as a means of information management during the approximately thirty-month-long Nigerian civil war as an inductive foundation. Due to our limited understanding of the civil war outside of what we could infer from interpretive sources, we used an inductive methodology to gather data from the respondents. This strategy allowed us to easily connect with and interview five baby boomers (persons born between 1946 and 1964) in Abakaliki Town, Ebonyi State, Nigeria, all of

whom were first-hand witnesses to the war and dependent on radio broadcasts for information as it unfolded. Due to Abakaliki's proximity to Enugu (the former capital of the defunct Biafra Republic) and being a significant settlement region for the war survivors of Igbo descent, the location was deemed suitable for the interviews. Hence, our major method of investigation was a series of in-depth, qualitative interviews with the target population.

When conducting historical research, it is frequently advantageous to utilise a somewhat limited sample size (Morgan, 2002). By restricting our attention to a narrower segment of the population (five participants), we successfully circumvented the influence of biases and extraneous information. The advanced age of the participants facilitates enhanced resource allocation and comprehensive provision of care during the study. Due to the reduced number of participants in the sample, we were able to allocate sufficient time and attention to the data collation process. A deeper understanding of the few individuals' behaviours, habits, and patterns also led to the acquisition of more intricate discoveries.

Data Collection

Our initial discourse revolved around a comprehensive analysis of our existing knowledge pertaining to the Civil War and the ramifications of radio technology, as well as identifying the gaps in our understanding. Several parameters of the power of radio were investigated in the conversation with the study participants. One parameter considered was the capacity of radio broadcasts to effectively reach and inform audiences nationwide. The disruption of radio broadcasts between some Nigerian territories and Biafran territories can be attributed to the probable impact of gunfire on the transmission lines (Onuoha, 2011). The examination also encompassed the parameter of radio broadcast content and Communication. Conducting research on this subject necessitates an examination of the message contained inside radio broadcasts, encompassing news reports,

propaganda, and appeals for action. Valuable observations pertaining to the impact of radio on public opinion or the conflict can be derived from a discussion of the content of these broadcasts. The investigation of the impact of radio on listeners' responses and engagement proved to be an adaptable parameter as well. The evaluation of individuals' responses to radio broadcasts of information was conducted for this objective.

In light of these parameters, the interviews exhibited a commendable level of structural integrity, albeit with a tendency to occasionally diverge from the predetermined line of questioning, instead delving into supplementary inquiries. The collation of relevant data was accomplished through the conversion of audio recordings of the interviews into written form. To accurately represent the narratives and reactions of the participants without any alterations or modifications, the collated data were carefully organised with the purpose of facilitating a comprehensive examination of the objectives at hand.

Thematic Analysis

The collated data underwent a process of categorisation and organisation, wherein they were systematically labelled and classified according to the thematic elements inherent in the posed inquiries. Three key concepts emerged as notably significant. The three predominant focal points revolved around radio technology, information management, and development. Within the designated segment of the research paper, denoted as the "Discussion" section, the following triad of concepts is presented to the discerning reader. The emphasis lies predominantly on the substance of the assertions rather than their manner of articulation. The process of selecting specific expressions that most aptly exemplify each theme was undertaken.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Theme of Radio Technology

In response to research objective one, an interviewee in the study revealed that at the start of the war, for him, listening to the radio went

beyond being a source of enjoyment and became a means of figuring out how to stay alive. Another interviewee recalled listening to radio broadcasts that detailed the progress of federal forces, their external allies, and their indulgences. These responses align with Davies (1997), who found out that the Eastern Nigeria Broadcasting Corporation (ENBC), sometimes known as Radio Biafra, was the wartime broadcasting studio, airing programmes in both the vernacular and English. As gathered from the conversation and in line with Davies's finding, the radio station was a lifeline for those who relied on it for news. Following the war, it was relocated to Enugu, and its name changed to the East Central State Broadcasting Service (ECBS). When the states of Anambra and Imo were split off in 1976, the name was shortened to "Anambra Broadcasting Service." Osa (2011) also shows that because of personnel being let go on March 16, 1992, following the founding of the new states of Anambra and Enugu in 1991, the Anambra Broadcasting Service, Enugu gave rise to the Anambra Broadcasting Service (R/TV) in Awka and the Enugu State Broadcasting Service (ESBS) in Enugu.

According to one of the interviewees, one of the primary factors in saving lives during the conflict was the acquisition of information through radio broadcasts. This assertion aligns with Doron's (2014) argument that during times of war, the availability of dependable and timely information plays a vital role in safeguarding and promoting the welfare of individuals impacted by the conflict. There exists a potential for the utilisation of radio broadcasts to disseminate news, updates, and warnings expeditiously and dependably to the general populace. Individuals residing in this region characterised by distress can now remain updated on current occurrences, potential dangers, and tactical manoeuvres, enabling them to make judicious choices regarding the most effective means of safeguarding themselves and their families. Armand, Atwell, and Gomes (2020) also assert that propaganda and disinformation are commonly utilised tactics to manipulate public sentiment and incite discontent in periods of

conflict. Radio broadcasts, on the other hand, served as a dependable means to obtain accurate information and counteract the dissemination of false information and deceit.

Theme of Information Management

In response to research objective two, one of the interviewees pointed out that possibly because content creators knew that generating any information by accident could be even more disastrous than the bullets from the enemies' rifles, adding that the role of the radio in the dissemination of safety information and for armed mobilisation was better appreciated during the crisis period. This claim is in line with Armand et al. (2020) who argue that radio transmissions can be trusted even when the area is experiencing high levels of tension and complete misinformation.

Another interviewee recalled that when the anthem was played and the voice of the regional military governor, Colonel Odumegu Ojukwu, was heard on the set, many people's attention was riveted on the radio. The conversation revealed that the radio broadcasts throughout the civil war were a purposeful, calculated, and extremely persuasive framework for the disturbed public, and this is in line with Kumar (2006) who states that the public's need for hope and morale maintenance is considered when creating radio broadcasts during times of war. By highlighting positive developments, sharing stories of perseverance, and disseminating supportive messages, radio broadcasts can help ease stress and worry in the community.

Shoemaker and Reese (2013) also argue that making emotional and irrational decisions during times of war never leads to better outcomes. Hence, radio messages are carefully crafted to encourage people to think critically by presenting unbiased facts, reasonable analysis, and insightful commentary. By presenting reasonable reasons and encouraging a measured response, these broadcasts help defuse tension and prevent rash actions that could make the situation worse.

Theme of Development

In response to research objective three, an interviewee in the study admitted that the radio has a deeper reach than the newest forms of mass Communication and will thus always play an important part in the spread of information. Another interviewee highlighted a problem with the new media, saying that its reach is restricted since not everyone has the knowledge to fully use its possibilities. The interviewee presented himself as an example, stating that he has no idea if he has ever checked into any of his social media handles created for him, but turning on the radio and letting the audio play on its own eliminates the need for technical knowledge to obtain information. These findings are congruent with those of Callejas and López-Cózar (2009), who found that the radio is a more effective companion for the elderly population. It is also thought that the radio, as a mass medium, might reach a large audience across all demographics with strategic information that would motivate people to act in support of sustainable development.

According to Krause (2020), the elderly have a specific fondness for radio as a source of information because of the medium's long and illustrious history. They have become accustomed to radio over the course of their lives and find it easy to access information through it. It is also clearly established that radio broadcasts can be trusted as a credible and reliable source of news (Krause, 2020). People of an elderly age who place a premium on trustworthiness in news outlets can learn from radio broadcasts that cover topics related to sustainable development.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Nigeria, a nation of considerable magnitude, exhibits a resolute determination to propel forward and foster progress. Radio, being the preeminent and extensively diffused medium within the nation, bears the responsibility of guiding the populace towards the trajectory of advancement. According to estimations, Nigeria is home to a minimum of 250 discrete ethnic groups, each characterised by their unique historical narratives, cultural practises, and

linguistic systems. To foster cohesion and facilitate the advancement of a nation, it is imperative to establish and maintain a system of Communication that is both efficient and effective. This inquiry pertains to a medium that possesses the ability to transcend geographical boundaries, overcome all obstacles, and exert a transformative influence on its viewership. Radio transmission is widely recognised as a paramount means by which individuals acquire information in contemporary society. The utilisation of radio technology during the Nigerian civil war played a pivotal role in enabling Communication, thereby fostering the dissemination of information and, to a somewhat lesser degree, bolstering the security landscape within the nation.

Radio serves as an exemplary medium for the acquisition of data and information, functioning as a catalyst for national development and societal progress. Due to this circumstance, it is imperative for every nation to acknowledge the significance of radio news broadcasts. The utilisation of technology devices by a specialised collective to disseminate symbolic content via radio waves, thereby cultivating a diverse and geographically dispersed viewership, remains consistent irrespective of the overall economic prowess of the nation. To exaggerate the influence of radio as a medium for disseminating information to the public would be an injustice to its authentic magnitude. Radio transmission is an effective means of disseminating information to a vast audience simultaneously, owing to its inherent advantages of temporal and spatial flexibility, as well as its ability to transcend literacy barriers. This study demonstrates the emergence of radio technology as a central element in the assessment discourse pertaining to the subject of sustainable development within contemporary society.

Limitation of Study

There is a perception that studies of the protracted Nigerian civil war are out of date and unreliable owing to the loss of proximity quality, but lessons can still be learnt by comparing events from the past with those of the present. Due to a lack of

literature on the topic of media communication and radio engagements during the Nigerian major armed crisis (1967-1970), our study ran into an empirical roadblock. The urgency of this study was largely driven by the need to address this void in the existing literature.

Ethical Consideration

Prior to the collection of the data from the sampled population, it was considered necessary to pre-inform them of the objectives of the study and how valid their responses would be in the studies. Based on this information, the interviewees had willingly participated in the research on the grounds that all information provided by them would be treated anonymously and with confidentiality.

Declaration

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